

A Study of ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of Male & Female B.Ed. Students

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study is to compare the ICT Competency & Social Intelligence of B.Ed. students of district Saharanpur. This is a survey study under descriptive research. For the present study, the population was all the male and female B.Ed. students in the degree colleges of district Saharanpur, U.P. in which 120 students were selected purposely (60 male & 60 female) as samples. For the collection of the data researcher administrated the ICT Competency Scale by Manmohan Gupta & Social Intelligence Scale by N.K. Chadha & Ms. Usha Ganeshan. Data collected were analysed by applying t-test and Pearson's coefficient of correlation (r). The level of significance was kept 0.01 & 0.05 to test the hypotheses. It was observed from the findings on ICT Competency and Social Intelligence, there is a significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students. Research also concludes that there is relationship between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence.

Keywords: ICT Competency, Social Intelligence, B.Ed. students.

Introduction-

Today's society, driven by scientific progress and generalized use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), has witnessed changes that reach all areas of human activity, particularly the education field, thus changing the way we teach and learn.

In 1985 with the introduction of computers in schools, and afterwards with the Internet emergence, approximately 15 years ago, significant changes took place in the way we conceive education. According to Graells, new learning processes and methods have been created, such as: means of expression, communication channels to access knowledge, interpersonal and cooperative work communication channels, interchange of information and ideas, new management instruments, new diagnosis instruments, new interactive resources, psychomotor and cognitive development. You may change it and link ICT competence of students with Social Intelligence, because nowadays, more than ever, new ways of feeling have to be considered in the learning process, that is, it is necessary that those who act in their environment have the ability to understand and express emotion, so that they can comprehend it and take maximum advantage of it in understanding themselves and the others.

Therefore, taking advantage of the growing motivation towards digital technologies among young people, it would be useful to promote their social skills, so that in later studies we can build support programs for teachers that will allow them to work on student's assertiveness, thus avoiding school conflicts. In a primary stage, our study will focus on a significant sample of students, ICT users, from several third cycle and colleges, will only determine these students Social Intelligence. For it, comprises a group of social intelligence associated to Patience, Recognition of social environment, Confidence, Sensitivity, Sense of humour, Cooperativeness. Tactfulness and Memory dimensions allow him to express himself, relate to others and understand himself and others.

Review of Related Literature:

Birnie & Horvath, 2002; Granovetter, 1973; Kraut, Kiesler, Boneva, Cummings, & Helgeson, 2002, investigated On ICT Competency and concluded that three primary theories were used to conceptualize the effect of ICT on individuals. Social network, social compensation, and rich-get-richer social network theory provides a framework through which to understand individual use of ICT and assumes that, in general, people exist within

a social network and continually seek to increase that network. As they do so, they increase their consumption of media, such as ICT, traditional voice telephones, or face-to-face communication that most readily facilitate that expansion.

Sanwal and Sareen, 2021, conducted research on Social Intelligence enables people to comprehend life better, make it more fruitful, and also ease the process of retirement.

Significance of the Study-

In modern era, ICT Competency and Social Intelligence, both are necessary and have an important role in Teacher Education. The present study shows that when ICT Competency of male and female students are considered, then it has significant difference between them. When Social Intelligence of male and female students are considered, then it has no significant difference between them. While on the other hand, there is a significant relationship between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of the male students studying at B.Ed. as well as female students studying at B.Ed.

Statement of the problem-

A study of ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of male and female B.Ed. Students.

Objectives-

- To compare the ICT Competency of male & female B.Ed. students.
- To compare the Social Intelligence of male & female B.Ed. students.
- To study the relationship between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of male B.Ed. students.
- To study the relationship between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of female B.Ed. students.

Hypotheses-

- There is no significant difference between ICT Competency of the male and female students studying in B.Ed.
- There is no significant difference between Social Intelligence of the male and female students studying in B.Ed.
- There is no significant relationship between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of male students studying at B.Ed.
- There is no significant relationship between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of female students studying at B.Ed.

Delimitations of the Study-

- The present study has been confined to students at studying at B.Ed.
- The present study has been confined to students of Saharanpur District of U.P.

Research Method- Descriptive survey method was used in the present study.

Sample- The sample for the present study consisted of 120 B.Ed. students studying in Saharanpur district. 60 female students and 60 male students were taken as sample of the study. They were selected in equal proportion gender-wise. Sample was selected by simple random sampling technique.

Variable- There are two variables. Dependent variable is ICT Competency and Independent variable is Social Intelligence.

Tool Used- Tools used for the study were -

- ICT Competency: ICT Competency Scale by Dr. Manmohan Gupta.
- Social Intelligence: Social Intelligence Scale by Dr. N.K. Chadha, Ms. Usha Ganeshan.

Statistical Techniques: Mean, Standard deviation, t-test and Product moment coefficient of correlation (r).

Analysis and interpretation of data-

Table-1
Showing significance of difference between mean scores for
ICT Competency of male and female B.Ed. students

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t value	Level of significance
Male	60	110.4	15.80	118	2.118	Significant at 0.05 level
Female	60	115.98	13.01			

Table-1 shows that calculated t-value for ICT Competency of male and female B.Ed. students is 2.118, which is significant of table value at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is significant difference between ICT Competency of the male and female students studying in B.Ed. So, hypothesis-1 is rejected. Table -1 also depicts that mean of female B.Ed. students for ICT Competency is higher than the mean of male B.Ed. students. So, it may be interpreted that ICT Competency among female students is higher than the ICT Competency among male students.

Table-2
Showing significance of difference between mean scores for Social Intelligence of male and female B.Ed. Students

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t value	Level of significance
Male	60	116.53	11.44	118	0.7419	Not Significant
Female	60	118.06	11.15			

Table-2 indicates that the calculated t-value for Social Intelligence of male and female B.Ed. students is 0.7419, which is less than table value at 0.05 level of significance. So, hypotheses-2 is accepted. Therefore, there is no significance difference between mean scores of Social Intelligence of male and female students studying in B.Ed. It may also be interpreted that Social Intelligence of male and female B.Ed. students is similar.

Table-3
Showing significance of relationship between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of Male B.Ed. students

	N	R	Level of Significance
ICT Competency	60	+0.6747	Significant at 0.01 level
Social Intelligence	60		

It is clear from Table-3 that the calculated coefficient of correlation (r) comes out to be 0.6747, which is more than table value at 0.01 level of significance. Hence, there is a significant relationship between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of the male students studying in B.Ed. So, hypothesis-3 is rejected. Table-3 also shows that there is a positive correlation between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of the male students studying in B.Ed. Therefore, if ICT Competency among male students studying in B.Ed. increases, then Social Intelligence among male students studying in B.Ed. increases or vice-versa. This correlation is of moderate level.

TABLE-4
Showing Significance of Relationship Between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of Female B.Ed. students

	N	R	Level of Significance
ICT Competency	60	+0.4160	Significant at 0.01 level
Social Intelligence	60		

It is clear from Table-4 that the calculated coefficient of correlation (r) comes out to be 0.4160, which is more than table value at 0.01 level of significance. Hence, there is a significant relationship between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of the female students studying in B.Ed. So, hypothesis-4 is rejected. Table-4 also shows that there is a positive correlation between ICT Competency and Social Intelligence of the female students studying in B.Ed. Therefore, if ICT Competency among female students studying in B.Ed. increases, then Social Intelligence among female students studying in B.Ed. increases or vice-versa. This correlation is of low level.

Conclusions

It is concluded that ICT Competency of female B.Ed. students is higher than male B.Ed. students while Social Intelligence of male and female B.Ed. students is similar. Also, ICT Competency and Social Intelligence are positively and significantly correlated in case of both male and female B.Ed. students. As the B.Ed. students are the learners and they would be the teachers. And they will play an important role after becoming a teacher to make the destiny of our students and that's why our nation.

The present study will be beneficial for the teachers with the conceptual framework that both ICT Competency and Social Intelligence plays an important role in the learning process. A teacher will be able to carry out learning well when supported by high ICT Competency and stable Social Intelligence. A teacher who has high ICT Competency level will be enthusiastic in carrying out their duties and always try to improve their skills.

The findings of the present study may be beneficial for the students also. In the world of education student performance is the result achieved by the student in carrying out tasks based on skills experience and sincerity and the use of time in the teaching and learning process in school and college. The student is an important part in the education system, so that it's performs becomes a matter that needs attention. Students' performance can be observed from the indicators of performances. Implementation of teacher performance relates to several factors such as ICT Competency and Social Intelligence. Teacher's professional and social views along with content will be a sound source of inspiration for the students and will be helpful in making them.

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